

UNIVERSITY OF PISA

Bachelor's degree in Computer Science

**A user-friendly framework for cross-device
asynchronous Federated Learning**

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Chapter 1

Introduction

It is estimated that over 4.6¹ billion smartphones and more than 30² billion IoT devices are in use worldwide, a number that is constantly growing [ASA⁺21]. IoT and mobile devices generate an extraordinary volume of data daily, from text messages to biometric parameters, from online transactions to consumption habits, up to data collected by environmental sensors and wearables. According to the International Data Corporation (IDC), the volume of data generated by IoT globally could reach 180 zettabytes (ZB) by 2020 [SPX19]. Such information represents a huge opportunity for Machine Learning and for the development of predictive models capable of transforming raw data into knowledge. However, the traditional machine learning paradigm requires that data be collected, centralized, and processed in dedicated data centers or on cloud servers. Although this approach has been widely used, it presents increasingly evident critical issues both in terms of scalability and respect for privacy.

The Challenges of Data Centralization

Data centralization involves two major issues. The first concerns the size of the data itself, which requires significant network resources for their transfer. With billions of devices generating data in real time, the infrastructures needed to support this continuous flow of information become extremely expensive both to implement and maintain. Furthermore, the centralized storage of such volumes of data, which requires physical and energy infrastructures that are unsustainable on a large scale, exacerbates the environmental impact problem and significantly increases operational costs to ensure service continuity.

The second issue, perhaps even more critical than the first, concerns data privacy and security.

¹<https://www.gsma.com/r/somic/>

²<https://www.unipoltech.com/it/news/scenario-iot>

Transferring large amounts of sensitive data, such as personal information, health data, or financial details, to a single central entity introduces significant risks. Privacy breaches, unauthorized access, cyberattacks, and misuse of data are some of the main threats associated with this approach. These concerns are heightened by the growing attention of international regulations, such as the *General Data Protection Regulation* (GDPR) in Europe [gdp], which impose increasingly stringent standards for the management and protection of personal data.

A New Paradigm: Federated Learning

In response to these challenges, Federated Learning (FL) [MMRyA16] emerges as an innovative paradigm that allows overcoming the limitations of centralized Machine Learning. This approach enables moving the computation to the data, rather than transferring the data to the computation. In other words, models are trained directly on local devices, such as smartphones, tablets, or IoT sensors, using the data present and collected on the device itself. Only the updated model parameters are sent to a central server for aggregation, thus preserving privacy and drastically reducing the amount of data transmitted.

Federated Learning offers an effective response to privacy and scalability issues. The ability to train models directly on devices opens new perspectives for machine learning, especially in critical sectors such as healthcare, finance, and consumer applications. For example, automatic word completion on smartphone keyboards (e.g., Google’s Gboard [HRM⁺18]) or voice recognition systems in virtual assistants (e.g., Apple Siri [LHW⁺21]) are already concrete examples of Federated Learning applied on a large scale today.

The Challenges of Federated Learning

Despite the advantages, implementing an efficient, scalable, and sustainable Federated Learning system in cross-device contexts, i.e., on highly distributed networks composed of a large number of heterogeneous devices, is not a trivial task. The devices participating in these systems vary greatly in terms of computational resources, memory capacity, and connectivity. Furthermore, the data collected by these devices are often not independent and not identically distributed (non-i.i.d.), reflecting the unique characteristics of users or the contexts in which they are generated. This statistical heterogeneity complicates the creation of a global model that is representative and performant for all participants [LHY⁺20].

From an infrastructural point of view as well, Federated Learning poses significant challenges. Managing millions of devices implies the need for robust communication protocols and aggregation algorithms that can operate effectively despite the dynamic and unpredictable participation of de-

vices, many of which may disconnect during training. These aspects make it crucial to design resilient systems, capable of tolerating high communication latencies, as well as data communication errors and highly dynamic participation of communication network entities.

The Motivation and Objectives of the Thesis

While Federated Learning is establishing itself as a promising technology, the implementation of practical solutions that scale to cross-device networks requires advanced and transversal technical skills, often far from the main focus of a Machine Learning expert. The design of a Federated Learning system indeed involves solving problems related to system architecture, communication management, device synchronization, and optimization of aggregation algorithms. This can represent a significant obstacle for ML Model Developers and Data Scientists whose main objective in this context is to design and train models for specific use cases.

This thesis arises precisely from these considerations. The objective is to develop a user-friendly framework that makes the adoption of Federated Learning accessible even to developers not expert in distributed infrastructures. The proposed framework aims to simplify the implementation process, providing tools that allow developers to focus primarily on model definition and data collection, without having to worry about the underlying technical complexities.

Furthermore, the framework is designed to address the specific challenges of the cross-device context, integrating solutions for managing device heterogeneity, data statistical variability, and computational resource limitations. The ultimate goal is to offer a development environment that is transparent to the user, replicating the experience of a centralized system but benefiting from the distributed and privacy-preserving features of Federated Learning.

Structure of the Thesis

In the following chapters, the fundamental principles of Machine Learning and Federated Learning will be introduced, with particular focus on the challenges that characterize cross-device scenarios. The main approaches to manage device and data heterogeneity will be analyzed, as well as the software architectures that support federated learning. Subsequently, the currently available market solutions will be discussed and the structure of the framework developed as the subject of this thesis will be introduced, describing its technical features, the innovations introduced, and the experimental results obtained, highlighting its contribution to making Federated Learning more accessible, scalable, and effective.

Framework Code

The source code of the framework designed and developed in this thesis is public and downloadable from GitHub at the following link:

<https://github.com/mamodev/Async-Federated-Learnig>

Chapter 2

Background

This chapter presents the information and foundational knowledge necessary to understand the context of Federated Learning, with particular attention to its use in cross-device environments and the challenges it entails. The fundamental principles of federated learning will be introduced, a Machine Learning paradigm designed to preserve data privacy by distributing the training process across different devices. Key concepts such as statistical heterogeneity, asynchronous communication, and client management will also be explored, which are essential for understanding the complexities of a cross-device Federated Learning system.

This overview provides the reader with a solid foundation to appreciate the technical and methodological contribution of the work carried out in this thesis, which aims to develop a user-friendly framework for implementing asynchronous Federated Learning algorithms in cross-device contexts, addressing challenges of scalability, efficiency, and ease of use for the user.

2.1 Machine Learning

Machine Learning (ML) is a discipline of artificial intelligence that focuses on the development of algorithms and statistical models capable of learning and improving their performance through experience, without being explicitly programmed to perform a specific task. In practice, ML enables computers to identify patterns and infer rules from data, allowing them to make predictions or decisions based on new inputs.

Machine Learning models are trained using datasets, which may contain labeled or unlabeled examples. Depending on the type of learning and the nature of the data, ML is primarily divided into three categories:

- **Supervised Learning:** The model is trained on a labeled dataset, where each input example is associated with a desired output. The goal is to learn a function that maps inputs to correct outputs, enabling the model to make accurate predictions on new, unseen data.
- **Unsupervised Learning:** The model works with unlabeled data and seeks to identify hidden structures or patterns within the data. This type of learning is used for tasks such as clustering, where examples are grouped based on intrinsic similarities.
- **Reinforcement Learning:** The model, often called an agent, interacts with a dynamic environment and learns to take actions that maximize a cumulative reward. The agent makes sequential decisions, adapting based on feedback received from its previous actions.

For the purposes of this thesis, we focus on supervised ML, which can be described through the following phases:

- **Data Collection:** Data is acquired from various sources, such as mobile devices, sensors, web applications, or company databases. This data may include structured or unstructured information and often contains sensitive or personal data.
- **Data Transfer and Centralization:** The collected data is transferred through communication networks to the central server. This process can involve sending large volumes of data, requiring significant bandwidth and introducing potential security risks during transfer.
- **Model Training:** The Machine Learning model is trained using pre-processed data. This involves the use of optimization algorithms to minimize a loss function, adjusting the model parameters to improve its ability to make accurate predictions.

- **Validation and Testing:** The trained model is evaluated on a validation dataset to measure its performance and prevent issues like overfitting. If necessary, hyperparameter tuning processes are iterated or alternative architectures are explored to improve results.
- **Implementation and Deployment:** Once the model meets the desired performance criteria, it is deployed in a production environment. This may include integration into software applications, web services, or embedded systems, where the model provides predictions or makes decisions in real time.

Machine Learning has revolutionized numerous sectors, including speech recognition, natural language processing, computer vision, and predictive analytics. However, the traditional training approach involves collecting and centralizing data from various sources, an approach that can entail significant risks in terms of privacy, security, and regulatory compliance. These risks arise from the transfer and storage of potentially sensitive data in a single location, exposing it to greater vulnerability to unauthorized access and possible privacy breaches.

2.2 Federated Learning

Federated Learning (FL) is an innovative supervised machine learning technique that enables the training of artificial intelligence models on data that remains distributed across different sources, without the need to centralize the data in a single point. It inverts the classic paradigm of centralized machine learning by moving model training where the data is located instead of moving the data where the model training occurs. In centralized machine learning, data from different sources is collected and transferred to a central server or data center. Here, the data is processed and used to train the machine learning model. In Federated Learning, the computation is moved to the data. Instead of transferring the data to a central server, model training occurs locally on the devices that hold the data (examples of devices include smartphones, desktops, and sensors with computing capabilities). Only the updated model parameters are sent to a central server, where they are aggregated to update the global model, ensuring that personal data is never exposed or transferred.

Federated learning is particularly important in contexts where data privacy and security are crucial, such as in the healthcare or financial sectors. Additionally, it allows leveraging distributed computing power, reducing the need for expensive and complex centralized infrastructures, as well as reducing the bandwidth requirements necessary for transmitting large datasets to a single processing center.

Illustratively, we can state that:

- Centralized Machine Learning involves moving the data to the computation
- Federated (Machine) Learning involves moving the computation to the data.

In Figure 2.1, the logical architecture of the federated learning approach is schematized. This architectural model was introduced by Google in 2016 to preserve user privacy and reduce the need to transfer large amounts of sensitive data [MMRyA16].

Cross-Silo vs Cross-Device

The term Federated Learning was initially introduced with particular emphasis on applications for mobile and Edge devices, therefore on a very large scale. The term “Edge” refers to devices or computing nodes positioned at the edges of the network, close to the data sources or end users. These include smartphones, IoT sensors, and small local servers that perform processing directly on site, thereby reducing latency and the load on the central network. Unlike the traditional Cloud architecture, where data is sent to centralized data centers for processing and storage, the Edge

Figure 2.1: Logical architecture of federated learning. The models indicated as *Model 1, ..., Model N* are trained locally on different devices and accessing exclusively local data accessible to the device. The data obtained from the training of local models (e.g., parameters or weights) are sent to a central aggregated model (Aggregated Model) in the Cloud, which can then be retransmitted as an update to the local model to the devices.

architecture shifts part of the computational load to peripheral devices. This enables faster processing and lower bandwidth usage, as the data does not need to be fully transmitted to the Cloud.

However, interest in applying Federated Learning has significantly expanded, including scenarios involving a limited number of relatively reliable Clients. An example of these scenarios is the collaboration between multiple distinct organizations that want to cooperate to train a model without sharing each organization's data. These two distinct Federated Learning settings have given rise to two distinct architectural models called *Cross-Silo* and *Cross-Device*.

Cross-Silo Federated Learning. This FL architectural model involves organizations, companies, or groups of clients. In this scenario, the number of participants is usually small (e.g., a few hundred), but each local entity possesses a significant amount of local data. A practical example of Cross-Silo Federated Learning is the collaboration between medical institutions to train disease prediction models using sensitive patient data from each center. In this context where the number of participants in model training is relatively small and typically corresponds to organizations like companies or institutions, each has access to large volumes of data and reliable large computational resources. In this scenario, entity participation in federated learning is more stable and coordinated, thanks also to reliable and high-speed network connections.

Cross-Device Federated Learning. This model involves mobile devices such as smartphones, wearable sensors, and IoT devices. In this case, the number of Clients can reach extremely large values (hundreds of thousands or millions), but each Client has a relatively small amount of local data. This approach requires the participation of a large number of edge devices to succeed. This configuration presents some peculiar challenges, such as the dynamic and unpredictable participation of devices, limited resources (in terms of computational capacity, memory, and battery), and variability in connections that can be unstable.

In summary, Cross-Silo Federated Learning is suitable for scenarios where few organizations collaborate using large amounts of data and significant computing resources, while Cross-Device Federated Learning is typical of scenarios where many (or very many) devices with small amounts of data and relative computing power collaborate to train a global model.

For the purposes of this thesis, we will limit ourselves to analyzing mainly the cross-device context, which presents greater challenges and opportunities.

Examples of Federated Learning Applications

Federated Learning has found applications in various fields, demonstrating its effectiveness in preserving data privacy and improving model efficiency on decentralized devices. A relevant example is keyboard auto-completion on mobile devices, as implemented by Google in its Gboard service [LZZ⁺17]. In this case, models learn from users' typing data directly on their devices, avoiding the transfer of sensitive information to central servers and thus ensuring privacy.

Another example concerns virtual assistants integrated into smartphones, which use Federated Learning to refine voice recognition systems. Thanks to this approach, devices can learn from users' voice commands, improving comprehension capabilities without transmitting voice recordings to servers, minimizing risks to confidentiality.

In the healthcare sector, wearable devices collect health-related data, such as heart rate, blood pressure, and physical activity being performed. Through Federated Learning, these devices can train predictive models to monitor users' health conditions directly on the devices themselves, without transferring sensitive data to the application's reference Cloud. In this way, the confidentiality of personal information is ensured, preserving user privacy.

In all these applications, it is possible to recognize a common set of steps necessary to define the federated learning model. Illustratively, the main steps are listed below:

- **Initialization of the global model:** It begins with the initialization of the global model (and its weights) on the central server (called Master). The model can be initialized randomly or based on a previously trained model.

- **Client Selection:** The Master selects, with some policy, a subset of peripheral entities (called Clients) that must participate in a training round.
- **Providing the global model to Clients:** The parameters of the latest version of the model are sent to the Clients, along with the parameters necessary for the training phase, such as the number of epochs, batch size, learning rate, etc.
- **Local Training:** Each Client trains the model received from the Master using its own local data. At the end of training, the Client sends the updated local model to the Master and possibly also some non-sensitive metadata from a privacy perspective, such as the size of the dataset used.
- **Aggregation:** Once each selected Client has sent the training results, the Master combines all local models to create a new global model. The aggregation of local models can follow different strategies and algorithms; the simplest is called *Federated Averaging* (FedAvg) [MMRyA16], which calculates the weighted average of the local models using the size of each Client’s local dataset as the weight.
- **Convergence Check:** The learning process is an iterative process that is repeated until the global model converges.

Challenges of Federated Learning

Although Federated Learning presents numerous advantages over centralized Machine Learning, it is not without issues and significant challenges that must be addressed and resolved.

The *heterogeneity of systems and devices* participating in defining the aggregated model, and the *statistical heterogeneity* of the data introduce problems that have a non-negligible impact. **System heterogeneity** refers to the variability of hardware and connectivity characteristics among devices. Some devices may have very limited resources (and/or energy consumption limitations) and thus may not be able to sustain the training of complex networks. **Statistical heterogeneity** refers to the variation and non-uniform distribution of data among participating devices. In a distributed context across various devices, the data reflect the specific activities and characteristics of users or devices, introducing significant differences in local data statistics. This statistical variability can manifest in various ways:

- *Non-i.i.d. data distribution:* The local data on each device do not follow the same distribution (they are not “independent and identically distributed”).

- *Disparity in data quantity*: Each device may have a different amount of local data available for training.
- *Differences in data patterns*: Local data may contain different patterns depending on the context in which they are generated based on factors such as geographic region, personal preferences, and behavior.

System and statistical heterogeneity pose significant challenges for Federated Learning, as it makes it difficult to create a global model that works well for all Clients participating in the training. Specific algorithms, such as FedAvg [MMRyA16], must be adapted to handle this variability and ensure that the aggregation of local models leads to an effective global model, while respecting the unique characteristics of each Client. Moreover, they can introduce aspects such as:

- **Slowed Convergence**: Data heterogeneity slows the convergence of Federated Learning algorithms. [LHY⁺20]
- **Objective Inconsistency**: Aggregating models trained on non-i.i.d. data can lead to convergence to a stationary point of an objective function different from the real one. [WLL⁺20]
- **Model Instability**: The difference between local models and the global one, due to non-i.i.d. data, can lead to unstable convergence that may never converge to the global objective function. [KKM⁺19]

2.3 Computational System Heterogeneity

In [MMRyA16], the Federated Averaging (FedAvg) algorithm was introduced, which allows Clients to update their local models before sending the updated parameters to the central Server for aggregation. FedAvg assumes that each Client performs E epochs (iterations on its local dataset) using Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) [RM51] with a mini-batch size of B . Consequently, for a Client with n_i local data samples, the number of local SGD iterations is calculated as $t_i = E \cdot n_i / B$, a value that can vary significantly between Clients.

This variation is caused by computational system heterogeneity, an intrinsic aspect of Federated Learning where Clients have different computational resources and local dataset sizes. In particular, devices such as smartphones, tablets, and laptops differ in terms of processing capacity, available memory, and battery life, which affects the amount of computational work each Client can handle. Furthermore, even with equal computing resources, slowdowns can be caused by background processes, interruptions, memory limitations. In general, a device with a larger local dataset (n_i high) will require more iterations to complete E epochs, while a device with limited resources may encounter difficulties even in performing just a few of the planned iterations.

Heterogeneity among Clients also entails significant variability in local training performance, affecting both the speed of convergence and the quality of the aggregated model. To address this challenge, FedAvg and other Federated Learning algorithms must be designed to adapt to these differences, for example, by dynamically adjusting the number of epochs or batch size based on the device's resources. This adaptation aims to ensure that even Clients with limited resources can contribute to updating the global model, maintaining the effectiveness and efficiency of distributed training on a heterogeneous network of devices.

The duration of each round is thus determined by the slowest Clients (stragglers). In a context where the number of Clients is high and variations in device computational power and local iterations are significant, this approach is not optimal and prevents the system from scaling. In a Cross-Device configuration, moreover, devices are by definition unreliable and may go offline at any moment.

The main problem is that FedAvg does not allow participants to perform variable amounts of local work based on their underlying system constraints (it is common to simply eliminate devices that cannot compute the E epochs within a specified time window) [BEG⁺19].

In the classic FedAvg configuration, where Clients are not allowed to perform a variable amount of work and partial result aggregation is not permitted, model convergence is guaranteed [MMRyA16]. However, these assumptions are not reasonable in a Cross-Device context. As soon as these assumptions are relaxed, the risk is objective inconsistency, i.e., the global model may converge to a

stationary point of an objective function that does not correspond, which can be arbitrarily different from the real objective (as shown in Figure 2.2), or the model may not converge at all and cause unstable updates.

Figure 2.2: Effect of local training with homogeneous and heterogeneous epochs and hyperparameters. Green squares and blue triangles denote the minima of global and local objectives, respectively.

In FL, the global objective function is defined as follows: $F(x) = \sum_{i=0}^m n_i \cdot F_i(x)/n$, where m is the number of clients and $n = \sum^m n_i$ is the total number of samples. As demonstrated in [WLL⁺20], the standard average of models after heterogeneous local updates (consequently FedAvg) leads to convergence to a stationary point that does not belong to the original objective function $F(x)$, but to an inconsistent objective function $F_e(x)$, which can be arbitrarily different from $F(x)$ depending on the values τ_i (number of local epochs).

To gain insight into this phenomenon, observe Figure 2.2 where, if Client 1 (x_1) performs more local updates than Client 2 (x_2), the update $x^{(t+1,0)}$ moves away from the true global minimum x^* , heading toward the local minimum x_1^*

2.4 Statistical Data Heterogeneity

Statistical data heterogeneity largely determines the effectiveness and efficiency of the federated learning process. In a realistic Cross-Device context, training data is distributed across a large number of Client devices, each of which collects data independently and with unique characteristics, often not identically distributed and not independent.

As anticipated in the previous section, FedAvg has demonstrated empirical success in heterogeneous configurations as long as its stringent assumptions are maintained. In cases where these fail, methods like FedAvg have shown divergence in practice when data is not i.i.d. [SLS⁺18].

Statistical heterogeneity negatively affects the convergence of federated learning algorithms and the quality of the global model. When Client data is non-i.i.d., the directions of local model updates can be very different from each other, causing oscillations in the aggregation phase and slowing convergence [ZLL⁺18]. Moreover, the global model may not adequately represent the optimal local models, reducing overall performance.

Another issue related to data heterogeneity is *fairness*, as the learned model may show bias toward devices with a greater amount of data or, if devices are weighted equally, toward groups of devices that appear more frequently.

The consideration of choosing between a single global model and multi-model approaches in Federated Learning is particularly relevant, especially when local data on devices is non-i.i.d. If each device is able to perform training on its own local data, as required by Federated Learning, the natural question arises: is it always advantageous to aim for a single global model? A single global model undoubtedly offers some advantages. For example, it can be distributed to Clients without data or with limited data, ensuring a standardized and uniform solution for all participants. This approach is also useful when device data characteristics are fairly similar, or when statistical variability is minimal, making the model general and sufficiently effective for all.

However, in cases where the data is strongly non-i.i.d., a single global model may not be ideal, as it may fail to capture the peculiarities of each Client’s local data, resulting in overall performance degradation. In these scenarios, “multi-model” approaches such as Multi-Task Learning (MTL) and Meta-Learning can be more appropriate and effective [KMA⁺19].

- **Multi-Task Learning (MTL):** With MTL, each device trains a model that, while sharing part of the structure with the global model, is specifically adapted to the characteristics of local data. Essentially, MTL treats each local dataset as a distinct task, allowing the creation of models specific to each Client. This approach allows each device to optimize the model for its own context, maintaining a connection with the global model but allowing greater flexibility

and thus improving performance when data is heterogeneous.

- **Meta-Learning:** Meta-Learning aims to create a global model that is not simply static, but is designed to adapt quickly to new data. In Federated Learning, a Meta-Learning-based model can learn a global and generic structure that each device can further personalize on its own data, improving model effectiveness for scenarios with significant variability.

Furthermore, personalization through techniques such as local fine-tuning or meta-learning allows adapting a global model to each Client’s data, ensuring greater local precision.

Finally, statistical heterogeneity can have significant effects on privacy and security in Federated Learning. When local device data is non-i.i.d. and highly specific, local model updates can reflect particular distinctive details of a Client’s data. This can increase vulnerability to potential attacks, such as *gradient inversion attacks* [ZGW⁺22]. In these attacks, an adversary might use the information contained in model updates to infer original sensitive data, exploiting the uniqueness of patterns in local data. To mitigate these risks, advanced protection techniques such as *differential privacy* can be employed. Differential privacy adds controlled noise to model updates, making it more difficult for an attacker to infer specific information from a Client’s original data without unduly compromising the quality of global learning. This approach allows protecting sensitive information, balancing privacy and accuracy in Federated Learning [OA22].

Figure 2.3: Abstract schema of federated process communication in different architectures

2.5 Reference Software Architectures

In the context of Federated Learning, the system architecture plays a crucial role in determining the efficiency, scalability, and security of the distributed training process. There are several architectures proposed in the literature to manage various requirements and address Federated Learning challenges, each with its own advantages and disadvantages [ZBO20]. Below, we describe the four main types of software architecture.

Centralized Architecture The prevailing software architecture in current Federated Learning systems is the centralized one, in which a single Master node coordinates the entire network of peripheral devices as shown in Figure 2.3a. In this configuration, the Master communicates with all

clients, collects local models, performs aggregation, and distributes the updated global model to all devices. This architecture is particularly suitable for small-scale systems, as it is simple to implement and manage.

However, the centralized architecture presents some significant limitations:

- *Single point of failure.* The Master is a central element that, by definition, represents a potential vulnerability point. If the Master experiences an interruption, the entire learning process is compromised. Even if organizations or large companies can provide reliable central servers for some scenarios, having an always-available and powerful Master may not be feasible or desirable in more collaborative, distributed, or dynamic contexts [VBT16].
- *Bottleneck with many Clients.* When the number of Clients is high, the Master server may become a bottleneck, reducing efficiency and slowing the aggregation process. Lian et al. [LZZ⁺17]. have demonstrated that decentralized algorithms can outperform centralized systems in terms of performance in scenarios with numerous clients.

It should be noted, however, that with careful system design, it is possible to mitigate the impact of a large number of Clients even in a centralized system. For example, communication optimization techniques and resource management can improve system scalability, reducing latency and distributing the load more efficiently [BEG⁺19].

Hierarchical Architecture The hierarchical Federated Learning architecture represents an alternative to the traditional centralized approach, introducing intermediate coordination nodes, often regional, to manage groups of edge devices, as shown in Figure 2.3b. In this configuration, local devices communicate with regional nodes, which in turn handle model aggregation and updates for devices within their geographic or logical area, before sending the information to the central server. This approach offers several advantages over the centralized architecture:

- *Reduction of communication bottlenecks.* Regional nodes distribute the communication load, reducing congestion and delays in data and update transmissions. This makes the architecture more scalable, especially for medium-sized applications, where the number of devices is high but not at the level of large global networks.
- *Energy and bandwidth efficiency.* With regional processing, edge devices do not always have to communicate directly with the central server, decreasing bandwidth and energy consumption, elements crucial in IoT and mobile contexts.

However, the hierarchical architecture still retains partial centralization, represented by the root server of the hierarchy, which remains a single point of failure. If the central server experiences

interruptions, the entire system may be affected. Moreover, this centralization, even if partial, can raise security and privacy concerns, as the management of aggregated information is still concentrated in a central node.

Regional Architecture The regional architecture represents a further step toward decentralization in Federated Learning, completely eliminating the central aggregation node and entrusting regional aggregation nodes with the task of managing model aggregation and communication between groups of devices, Figure 2.3c. This design presents several advantages, including:

- *Improved robustness.* The absence of a central node eliminates the risk of a single point of failure, increasing the overall resilience of the system. In case of interruption of a regional node, the impact is limited to the group of devices associated with that node, without compromising the entire network.
- *More localized model training.* In applications where data distributions are more similar among nearby devices (e.g., in geographic or specific sector contexts), regional nodes can aggregate models that better reflect local characteristics. This leads to more accurate models for specific groups of devices, improving performance without overly adapting the global model.

This architecture is particularly well-suited to scenarios with geographically distributed networks or where privacy and security needs require more autonomous data management among groups.

Decentralized Architecture The decentralized architecture in Federated Learning shifts aggregation responsibilities directly to edge devices, eliminating the need for central or regional coordination nodes, as shown in Figure 2.3b. In this configuration, each device autonomously contributes to model updating and sharing, distributing the computational and communication load across all participating nodes. This structure offers several key advantages, including:

- *Autonomy.* Since each device manages its own training and aggregation process, the architecture is highly autonomous. Devices can quickly adapt to local changes, modifying the model to respond to new environmental conditions or data without depending on a central node.
- *Adaptability.* With distributed aggregation, the architecture is highly flexible and suitable for dynamic and scalable systems like IoT networks, where devices can frequently connect and disconnect. The decentralized configuration allows greater resilience and reduced impact of individual failures on overall system results.

However, this architecture requires a robust infrastructure and presents high costs. Each device must have the capacity to perform local training and support communication for model transmission,

Characteristic	C	H	R	D
Level of centralization	High	Moderate	Low	None
Scalability	Limited	Medium	High	Very high
Single point of failure	Yes	Partially	Reduced	No
Communication bottleneck	Yes	Partially	Reduced	Minimal
Robustness	Low	Medium	High	Very high
Infrastructure requirements	Low	Moderate	Moderate	High
Management complexity	Low	Medium	High	Very high
Suitable system sizes	Small	Medium	Large	Very large

Table 2.1: Synthetic comparison between different Federated Learning architectures. C: Centralized Architecture; H: Hierarchical Architecture; R: Regional Architecture; D: Decentralized Architecture.

characteristics that can be demanding in terms of computational, energy, and network resources. Despite these requirements, the decentralized architecture represents an effective solution for large-scale applications and scenarios where privacy and resilience are priorities, offering a scalable Federated Learning system less vulnerable to bottlenecks and single points of failure. In fully decentralized learning, interaction with a central server is completely replaced by *peer-to-peer* communication between Clients. In this architecture, the communication topology is represented by a connected graph: the nodes of the graph are the Clients, while an arc between two nodes indicates the presence of a direct communication channel between two Clients. The network graph is designed to be sparse with a small maximum degree, limiting the number of connections per node. This design reduces the communication load for each device, as each Client sends and receives messages only from a limited number of nearby peers, reducing the computational and network burden. In this context, a round of decentralized learning corresponds to a cycle in which each client: a) performs a local model update using its own data, and b) exchanges the updated model or parameters with neighboring clients in the graph.

A fundamental characteristic of decentralized learning is the absence of a global model state, typical of classic federated architectures. Here, there is no single central model toward which all clients converge; instead, each client maintains a local version of the model, which evolves progressively thanks to parameter exchanges with neighbors. This decentralization allows greater flexibility and robustness, especially in contexts with high dynamism and where devices frequently connect and disconnect.

In light of what has been described for the reference architectures in Federated Learning, Table 2.1 summarizes the peculiar characteristics of each of them.

2.6 Asynchronous Federated Learning

The asynchronous approach in Federated Learning (AFL) represents an important innovation to overcome synchronization difficulties and improve performance in distributed systems. Unlike the synchronous approach, where the aggregator must wait for all devices to complete local training before generating a new version of the model and starting the next round, in AFL the model is updated every time a device sends its updated parameters. This mechanism offers some advantages [XKG19]:

- *Elimination of stragglers.* With AFL, slower devices (stragglers) do not slow down the entire system, as the model can be updated without waiting for all clients to complete their training. This improves overall efficiency and allows optimal use of computational resources.
- *Continuous model evolution.* The model updates incrementally as it receives new information, enabling rapid progression of learning and greater adaptability of the model to incoming data.
- *Improved scalability.* Each device can train the model according to its own computational capabilities and speed, without being penalized by the processing times of other participants. This makes AFL particularly suitable for large-scale systems, where devices have heterogeneous capabilities and participate dynamically

Despite the advantages in managing device heterogeneity, the asynchronous approach in Federated Learning introduces new challenges. First, managing *staleness* (obsolescence), i.e., the risk that updates sent by devices may not be temporally aligned with the current state of the global model. This can lead to an increase in error during the aggregation phase. Indeed, if a device sends an update based on data or a very outdated model compared to the latest version of the aggregated model, integrating such an update can cause increases in the overall system error. The lack of synchronization could lead to situations where the global model converges to non-optimal stationary points [WLL⁺20], compromising the quality of the final model, or worse, to instability of updates causing model divergence. Moreover, since devices do not wait for others to complete training, there is a risk of accumulating models that do not accurately represent the global dataset, especially in non-i.i.d. data scenarios.

Staleness represents an important challenge related to the timing of model updates. When a local device trains a model on its own data, it uses a version of the global model that was sent by the central server at a certain time. However, due to various factors such as differences in computing capabilities, network availability, and training completion times, there can be delays in sending updates from different devices.

Figure 2.4: Schematic comparison between synchronous and asynchronous aggregation

When a device sends its update to the server, this update may be based on a model that is no longer the latest global model available. This happens because, in the time elapsed since the device started local training, the server may have received and aggregated updates from other devices, thereby updating the global model. In other words, the update a device sends may refer to a model state that has been superseded by more recent changes made by other devices.

A commonly used strategy is not to aggregate updates sent by straggler clients. As examined in [SLS⁺18] for the FedAvg algorithm, it is noted that this strategy, when the number of stragglers is high, leads to slowed convergence and possible model instability.

The negative effect of stragglers is closely linked to statistical heterogeneity. In the case where data is i.i.d., convergence is slower but still guaranteed. As we will see in the section on the experiments conducted, the distribution of data labels across various Clients does not significantly impact convergence in the presence of stragglers.

To mitigate the challenges introduced by the asynchronous approach, there are hybrid techniques such as FedBuff and Hsync, which are discussed in the next section.

2.7 Known Optimizations

To address Federated Learning issues, several algorithms and optimization strategies have been developed that aim to improve the stability, efficiency, and robustness of the federated learning process.

FedProx - reduction of statistical and system heterogeneity . FedProx [SLS⁺18] is an extension of the FedAvg algorithm specifically designed to address system and data heterogeneity. FedProx introduces a regularization term μ that penalizes the difference between a Client's local model and the global model. This proximity term helps keep local updates close to the global model, even when local data is non-i.i.d., thereby improving convergence stability. Additionally, FedProx allows clients to perform a variable number of local iterations based on their computational capabilities, enabling less powerful devices to participate without the obligation to complete a fixed number of epochs.

FedAvgM - improving convergence with Momentum FedAvgM [HQB19]. is an extension of the FedAvg algorithm that introduces Server-side Momentum to improve convergence stability and efficiency, particularly in cases of statistical heterogeneity. Momentum is a technique commonly used in optimization algorithms to accelerate gradient descent, storing a fraction of the previous update direction and adding this term to the current gradient. By using Momentum, FedAvgM is able to dampen oscillations between Client updates, leading to faster and more stable convergence. This technique is particularly useful when data is non-i.i.d., as Momentum helps smooth differences between local updates and ensure a more uniform progression toward an optimal global model.

FedBuff - improving asynchronous aggregations with buffer FedBuff [NMZ⁺21] was developed to improve the efficiency of asynchronous aggregations, mitigating the impact of outdated updates (staleness). FedBuff uses a buffer to accumulate and aggregate updates from Clients in a more organized and strategic manner, so that updates are aggregated at optimal times, minimizing the negative effect of staleness on global model updates. This approach improves model stability even when devices participate asynchronously, optimizing computational resources.

Hysync - managing system heterogeneity with hybrid synchronization Hysync [SLW⁺20] is a hybrid solution that combines synchronous and asynchronous approaches to address system heterogeneity and improve aggregation efficiency. Hysync allows performing update synchronization in a more flexible manner, adapting the aggregation process to client capabilities. This approach

reduces the impact of slower clients (stragglers) and ensures that the global model continues to evolve without significant waits, maintaining high learning process efficiency.

FedNova - reducing variability with update normalization . FedNova [WLL⁺20] was proposed to address convergence problems due to variability in local iterations. FedNova introduces a client update normalization technique to ensure that each contribution to the global model is fair and proportional to the work performed, regardless of the number of epochs completed. This approach is particularly useful for mitigating the negative effects of system and statistical heterogeneity, ensuring that each device contributes in a balanced manner to the global model, thereby improving convergence.

SCAFFOLD - reducing variance for statistical heterogeneity . SCAFFOLD [KKM⁺19] is an approach designed to reduce the variance introduced by data statistical heterogeneity, introducing a gradient correction strategy. SCAFFOLD uses a technique based on an estimate of the difference between the local and global gradient to stabilize updates, significantly reducing variance and improving convergence stability. This approach enables faster and more precise convergence, making it particularly effective in contexts where local data differs considerably between devices.

FedGroup - aggregation for homogeneous groups for better personalization . FedGroup [DLJ⁺21] proposes an innovative approach to improve personalization and effectiveness of Federated Learning in contexts characterized by high data and device heterogeneity. Instead of applying the same global model to all clients, FedGroup divides devices into homogeneous groups based on common characteristics. Each group processes an intermediate model more representative of its own data, which is then refined with local updates. This method reduces the impact of non-i.i.d. variability among Clients, promoting more accurate personalization and better global model convergence, while preserving privacy.

Chapter 3

State of the Art

In recent years, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence have experienced rapid development, leading to increasing adoption of these technologies in numerous application areas. Parallely, the need to preserve user privacy and effectively manage highly distributed data has focused interest on Federated Learning (FL).

To support this innovative approach, numerous frameworks and libraries have been developed, each designed to address specific needs. These tools offer advanced functionalities for managing Cross-Silo and Cross-Device scenarios, two main categories that reflect the different configurations of Federated Learning.

As discussed in Chapter 2.5, Cross-Silo applies to scenarios where participating devices are organizational entities or controlled servers, with stable availability and high computational resources typical in areas such as collaboration between institutes or companies; Cross-Device adapts to scenarios where a vast network of personal devices participates in training, typical of highly heterogeneous environments characterized by unstable connections, limited resources, and dynamic participation.

The selection of the most suitable framework depends closely on the type of scenario and specific application requirements. Some frameworks focus on optimization for Cross-Silo scenarios, offering tools for coordination and centralized data management, while others are designed to address the complexity and scalability required in Cross-Device environments, integrating mechanisms for asynchronous training, device heterogeneity management, and robustness to errors.

3.1 Established Frameworks

With the development of Federated Learning, numerous frameworks have been introduced to the market, including TensorFlow Federated (TFF) [Fed], Flower [BTM⁺20], FederatedScope [XWG⁺22], PySyft [RTD⁺18], FedML [HLS⁺20], and OpenFL [?]. However, most of these frameworks primarily focus on the quality of the learned model, rather than optimizations related to the performance of the distributed infrastructure and the communications necessary for the federated process. Many of these tools are designed for Cross-Silo scenarios, while only a few, such as FederatedScope and Flower, can address the complexities of Cross-Device systems, characterized by unreliable devices and operating on a large scale.

A common property among these frameworks is the master-slave architectural pattern. Following the lines of the first FL algorithm FedAvg [MMRyA16], these frameworks have structured themselves to follow its synchronous and coordinated approach where there exists a central/decentralized entity that controls and coordinates the federated devices. A framework that seeks to depart from this architectural rigidity is FederatedScope, which is implemented with an event-based architecture, widely used in distributed systems. With this architecture, an FL paradigm can be defined as pairs of events and actions: participants wait for certain events (e.g., model parameters are transmitted to clients) to activate the corresponding handlers (e.g., model training based on local data). Therefore, users can express the behaviors of servers and clients from their own perspective independently, rather than sequentially from a global perspective. This flexibility allows creating a system capable of supporting scenarios with a large quantity of clients and defining different FL paradigms such as asynchronous learning in a trivial manner.

In the following, we briefly describe the main Federated Learning frameworks currently available.

TensorFlow Federated (TFF) [Fed]. Developed by Google, it is one of the most established frameworks for FL, built on the TensorFlow ecosystem [AAB⁺16]. It offers building blocks for implementing models, federated computations, and dataset management in Cross-Silo scenarios thanks to its ability to handle distributed data securely. TFF supports simulation across multiple machines and the creation of distributed architectures, but its real use in large-scale distributed environments requires additional configurations and is not optimized by default for such scenarios. TFF presents some limitations. For example, it does not directly integrate advanced privacy mechanisms such as *Differential Privacy* (DP) or *Secure Multi-Party Computation* (SMPC), but provides the foundations to implement such techniques. Developers must manually configure the desired privacy strategies. Additionally, TFF does not offer native tools to manage attacks such as data tampering (data poisoning) or client update manipulation (model poisoning). Therefore, the absence of predefined

mechanisms to mitigate these attacks makes this part of the statement true.

PySyft [RTD⁺18]. Developed by OpenMined, it introduces advanced functionalities for privacy protection, including SMPC and DP. This framework, compatible with both PyTorch [PGM⁺19] and TensorFlow [AAB⁺16], enables distribution on single machines or node networks, using WebSocket for communication. PySyft is particularly useful for developing applications where data security is a priority.

SecureBoost [CFJ⁺19]. It is a framework specialized in building decision trees in scenarios with vertically partitioned datasets. Using encryption strategies, SecureBoost [CFJ⁺19] enables different parties to collaborate without revealing sensitive information, ensuring high accuracy in distributed contexts.

FederatedScope and FedML [XWG⁺22] [HLS⁺20]. They offer further levels of flexibility. FederatedScope, thanks to an event-based architecture, supports synchronous and asynchronous strategies, attack simulation, and privacy protection. FedML, on the other hand, integrates communication protocols such as gRPC [gRP] combined with Protocol Buffers [Sch12] (briefly gRPC/Proto), MPI [Ope], and MQTT [MQT], adapting to different configurations, from IoT devices to high-performance Cross-Silo infrastructures. With its FedML-core and FedML-API modules, this framework allows standalone simulation, distributed computing, and on-device training.

LEAF [CWL⁺18]. It stands out as a benchmarking tool for FL, providing distributed datasets and partitioning mechanisms useful for evaluating the performance of other frameworks.

OpenFL [Ope24]. OpenFL is an open-source framework designed for Federated Learning (FL), supporting both distributed training and data privacy protection. It distinguishes itself with its modular architecture, allowing users to easily customize system components and integrate different federated learning algorithms. OpenFL [Ope24] is compatible with popular deep learning frameworks like TensorFlow [AAB⁺16] and PyTorch [PGM⁺19], and offers advanced node communication management, reducing latency and optimizing the efficiency of the distributed system. It is particularly suitable for scenarios where performance must be balanced with the protection of sensitive data, such as in healthcare or financial applications.

Flower [BTM⁺20]. Flower is a flexible federated framework that supports large-scale distributed training. Designed to be highly modular, Flower enables users to easily implement and test different federated learning strategies, such as global synchronization and customized aggregation tech-

Framework	Cross-	Scenario	Protocol	Implem.
TFF	silo	sim., real	gRPC/proto	Python
PySyft	silo/device	sim., real	Websockets	Python
SecureBoost	silo	simu., real	gRPC/proto	Python
FederatedScope	silo/device	sim., real	gRPC/proto	Python
LEAF	silo	sim.	-	Python
FedML	silo	sim., real	gRPC/proto, MPI, MQTT	Python/C++
OpenFL	silo	sim., real	gRPC/proto	Python
Flower	silo/device	sim., real	gRPC/proto	Python

Table 3.1: Summary comparison table of the discussed frameworks

niques. Flower is compatible with machine learning frameworks like TensorFlow [AAB⁺16], PyTorch [PGM⁺19], and scikit-learn, and offers efficient communication between clients and servers via gRPC [gRP]. Its design allows integration with different hardware and software infrastructures, making it ideal for edge device scenarios, IoT, or cloud applications. Flower is known for its ability to balance flexibility, ease of use, and scalability.

All the FL frameworks listed support a simulation mode, which allows experimenting and debugging a federated system locally. However, it is not guaranteed that they also support a real-world oriented distributed mode, such as TFF, SecureBoost, and OpenFL. From this perspective, the most limited FL framework is LEAF: this software is explicitly designed to be used only for benchmarking purposes.

Communication

A central element in the design of Federated Learning frameworks is how communication between different entities is implemented. Most tools, including TFF, FedML, Flower, and FederatedScope, use protocols such as gRPC/Proto for communication between Clients and Servers. This protocol ensures good performance, reducing latency and efficiently handling requests and responses in federated scenarios.

Frameworks like PySyft differentiate by adopting alternatives such as WebSocket, which provides persistent bidirectional connections. This approach is particularly suitable for optimizing real-time communication in scenarios with reduced latency requirements.

FedML, on the other hand, extends support to additional protocols such as MPI and MQTT, ensuring greater adaptability:

- **MPI** (Message Passing Interface) is ideal for high-performance environments like Cross-Silo contexts, where networks and computational resources are robust (e.g., clusters with high-performance networks).
- **MQTT** (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) targets IoT devices, offering low-energy and low-bandwidth communications, making it suitable for Cross-Device scenarios.

The choice of framework and communication protocol strongly depends on the characteristics of the application scenario and the constraints of privacy, scalability, and available resources that one aims to achieve. Table 3.1 reports the main characteristics of each Federated Learning framework, with the aim of highlighting their differences and providing a direct comparison of their functionalities, such as support for Cross-Silo or Cross-Device, the application scenario, the protocols used, and the programming language used for implementation.

Asynchronous Learning

Asynchronous federated learning represents a significant evolution over the traditional synchronous approach, offering advantages in terms of efficiency, scalability, and management of heterogeneity among participating devices. In an asynchronous environment, devices do not have to wait for the completion of all client updates before proceeding, reducing delays and improving the use of computational resources. However, despite these advantages, support for asynchronous learning in Federated Learning frameworks is still quite limited.

Most currently available frameworks, such as TensorFlow Federated, FedML, and OpenFL, have been designed to operate in synchronous and coordinated mode, with a strong focus on managing centralized communication rounds. This structure imposes synchronization among devices, which is incompatible with the requirements of asynchronous learning.

To support asynchronous algorithms, a significant revision of the underlying architectures is necessary, particularly of the aggregation and communication mechanisms. Even flexible frameworks like Flower, although they offer some functionalities for asynchronous scenarios, require substantial modifications for full support of this mode.

Currently, few frameworks explicitly support asynchronous learning:

- **FedML**: Includes experimental modules for supporting asynchronous scenarios, but integration is limited to specific contexts and is not optimized for large distributed networks.
- **Flower**: Allows flexible communication configuration, which facilitates some implementation of asynchronous algorithms. However, it lacks a native infrastructure for managing complex asynchronous updates.

Research in this field is exploring new architectures and communication protocols to improve support for asynchronism, addressing challenges such as update *staleness*, dynamic aggregation, and global model consistency. With the development of these approaches, an expansion of support for asynchronous learning in future frameworks is expected.

3.2 Considerations

The current landscape of Federated Learning offers a wide range of tools designed to meet different application needs. Frameworks like TensorFlow Federated, PySyft, FATE, Flower, OpenFL, and FedML stand out for their different levels of abstraction and ease of use. Some are optimized for quick and ready-to-use implementations, while others focus on customization and flexibility, making them suitable for users with advanced skills. However, managing asynchrony in Cross-Device contexts, characterized by heterogeneous devices and unstable connections, remains a significant technical challenge.

In this thesis work, we aimed to simplify access to these techniques, offering solutions that can be easily implemented even by a broader audience. This approach not only facilitates the creation of distributed and heterogeneous systems but also promotes the adoption of FL in scenarios where privacy and scalability are important requirements. In this way, it contributes to making Federated Learning more accessible by reducing technical barriers to its use.

Chapter 4

Software Architecture of the Proposed Framework

This chapter presents the software architecture of the framework developed in this thesis, designed to enable Federated Learning (FL) scenarios in highly heterogeneous and distributed environments. The framework stands out for its modular approach and the level of abstraction that makes its usage extremely intuitive for the end user. The main objective is to offer a system that, while managing the inherent complexity of federated learning, maintains a simple and familiar user interface, comparable to that of classic centralized learning scenarios and in some cases even more intuitive.

Objectives and Goals

The proposed framework aims to:

- Simplify the adoption of Federated Learning: allowing users to focus only on fundamental aspects, such as the training data flow, the model to train, and a minimal configuration.
- Manage heterogeneous environments: adapting to devices with varying computational and network resources, leveraging a "resource-driven" approach.
- Maximize modularity and flexibility: offering an easily extensible architecture to support future improvements, such as decentralized approaches or customized algorithms.
- Optimize performance: the framework is written in C, a high-performance language, and adopts parallelization patterns and non-blocking/asynchronous I/O, ensuring efficiency in communication management and model processing, even in scenarios with numerous clients and large data volumes.

- Improve communication efficiency: through the use of optimized TCP protocol, custom format messages, and advanced techniques such as model quantization and compression, the framework significantly reduces latency and bandwidth consumption. These mechanisms enable fast and scalable transfers even in the presence of large quantities of clients and frequent updates.

Figure 4.1: Abstract schema from the developer's perspective

Thanks to its design, the framework allows developers to leverage the potential of Federated Learning without needing to delve into the underlying technical implementation complexity. This "plug-and-play" philosophy is made possible by a high level of abstraction. The original idea is to provide an "out of the box" solution where the user provides only 3 inputs (Figure 4.1): The data flow for local training; The model to train; And a configuration containing connection information, the aggregation strategy to use. To not limit the customization of learning processes and therefore the flexibility of this product itself, the user can actually provide multiple configurations, for example by redefining some key logical functions of the learning process.

4.1 Resource Driven Learning

The framework proposed by this thesis differs significantly from the approach used by other available solutions discussed in the state-of-the-art section (cf. Chapter 3). In traditional Federated Learning, it is the central server that selects a subset of available devices and initiates and coordinates the learning process. The federated process is organized into rounds, and a round ends when all clients (or a certain threshold, depending on the implementation) have sent their local model. At the end of a round, the new global model is calculated, and the procedure restarts. Our proposal shifts the control of participation and sending of local models to the clients themselves that produce them. We believe that it is the client itself that can best evaluate whether it is the right time to contribute to improving the global model. For example, when it is believed that a relevant amount of data has been collected, or when computational resources allow it (for example, the battery level for a mobile or IoT device). Thus, it is the resources of the federated devices that drive the training process and not a central entity: it is no longer the central aggregator that selects clients to participate in training the global model, but the clients that contribute when they can to its improvement. To enable this "Resource driven" approach, the system must necessarily be asynchronous, which, as discussed earlier in the background section [2.4], brings scalability advantages but also significant instability issues in case of statistical heterogeneity. Figure 4.2 shows the learning process from the perspective of a federated client; as can be seen, the training process arises from a local event, whether temporal or otherwise. The "Force Sync" event is an event sent by the server (this can be disabled during configuration) before aggregation, as shown in Figure 4.3, and serves to force the termination of the training phase. This event is used for implementing algorithms like HySync [2.7]

Figure 4.2: UML Activity Diagram of the local training process of the federated model

The process that the server follows, on the other hand, is entirely passive and driven by the reception of updates from clients. Although outside the scope of this framework, a classic synchronous approach, like that proposed by most existing solutions, could be simulated. First, the server must be configured to aggregate models when a minimum number of updates has been received. This is a natively supported configuration since the server uses an update buffering strategy. The clients, like the server, do not undergo major changes: it is sufficient to replace the event that starts model

Figure 4.3: UML Activity Diagram of the aggregation process and global model creation on the server side

training with the notification of the presence of a new global model sent by the server. Below is pseudocode that shows what was just described.

```

1 loop:
2     wait_for_new_model()
3     model = get_latest_global_model()
4     local_model = train(model, data)
5     send_update(local_model)
  
```

4.2 Server Software Architecture

The objective of this thesis is to design a framework capable of managing Federated Learning scenarios in highly heterogeneous and distributed environments, which may involve a large number of clients. Although our initial approach employs a centralized architecture, it is designed modularly to support future scalable, reliable, and resilient implementations. The centralized architecture is adopted in this phase as a starting point to test the feasibility of the proposed solution. In the future, the framework may evolve toward a more decentralized federated architecture, with more distributed nodes and high availability systems. See section on federated architectures 2.5.

Language and Design The choice of the server’s implementation language is crucial to achieve high performance, especially in a Federated Learning context where communication management and model processing require high efficiency. Unlike many existing solutions that use Python (cf. Chapter 3), our framework is implemented in C, a systems language known for its performance. The use of C allows us to minimize execution time for the most critical operations and enables finer memory and resource management. The software architecture is designed with a focus on adopting performance-oriented patterns, such as the Producer-Consumer pattern, to manage model update queues and improve efficiency in I/O operations, and the Data Parallel pattern to reduce latencies and improve throughput. Figure 4.4 illustrates at a high level the structure of the server-side software system, whose components are introduced in the following paragraphs.

Client-Server Communication

For managing communication between Server and Client, the system adopts the TCP protocol, which ensures reliable message transmission. The choice of TCP is motivated by the need for a secure and stable channel for sending models and updates between Client and Server. Each communication message between the Server and the Clients is encoded according to a custom-defined format to optimize efficiency and reduce latency. To optimize the management of a large number of clients and concurrent requests, we have adopted an event-based architecture with non-blocking I/O, leveraging the *epoll* API [Epo], a feature of the Linux standard library. *Epoll* is particularly advantageous in high-concurrency scenarios, as it allows monitoring a large number of file descriptors without the need for repeated polling operations, significantly improving performance compared to other methods like `select` and `poll`. The use of *epoll* allows efficient handling of I/O connections, notifying the Server only when there is data to read or write, avoiding blocking of the main process and improving system responsiveness. Furthermore, *epoll* is highly scalable, as it supports managing thousands of

Figure 4.4: Server Software Architecture.

simultaneous connections with minimal overhead. To further increase the server’s capacity to handle a larger number of Clients, as illustrated in Figure 4.4, it is possible to use multiple threads (typically called *Workers*) to distribute the workload. In this context, the Linux kernel allows accepting connections on the same port from multiple threads without the need for complex synchronization mechanisms, thanks to the `SO_REUSEADDR` parameter. This parameter allows different threads to bind to the same port, making it possible to use a thread pool to handle incoming connections in parallel. Connections are distributed by the operating system in a Round Robin manner, assigning each connection to a specific thread for processing. In this way, each connection is completely isolated and managed by a single thread, ensuring scalable parallel management of requests. This architecture makes the system extremely efficient on multi-core architectures and is capable of horizontal scaling, allowing it to handle hundreds of thousands of simultaneous connections in a smooth and responsive manner.

Asynchronous Model Aggregation

Model aggregation occurs asynchronously. When updates arrive from Clients, they are first decompressed and normalized, then stored in a buffer. The buffering strategy determines when it is appropriate to proceed with model aggregation, based on the number of received updates and the flow management logic. Once the right moment for aggregation has been identified, weights are assigned to the models based on the federated optimization algorithm used. For example, in FedAvg, the weight of each model is proportional to the number of samples it was trained on. The weights may depend on other factors related to the specific optimization strategy. After weight assignment, a weighted average of the models is performed.

Both the aggregation phase and the pre-processing and averaging phases of the models can be executed in parallel. The pre-processing phase can adopt a pattern that combines *Farm* and *Pipelining* constructs, while the averaging phase can be managed through the *Reduce* pattern. These approaches enable optimization of model processing, fully leveraging parallelization to improve overall performance.

To manage large volumes of updates and high-dimensional models, all model-related operations use disk pagination with "Memory Mapped IO". This approach allows the system to avoid overloading main memory, enabling more efficient resource management, especially when handling large amounts of data. When aggregating models, for example, they are saved to disk, and one page at a time is aggregated to generate the new model. This allows the server to handle large quantities of updates without ever exceeding the available memory.

I/O Overhead and Memory Management

Communication between the communication and aggregation subsystems occurs through shared memory data structures. Each update is received divided into ordered chunks to reduce latency in packet handling and prevent memory overload. Each chunk, after being received, is placed into a processing queue.

A specialized thread handles the transfer of updates to disk, using asynchronous I/O to reduce overhead from context switches between the kernel and user space, as well as from blocking I/O. Once an update is fully written to disk (all its chunks have been saved), its identifier is inserted into the updates queue, which is subsequently read by the aggregation subsystem for processing.

A similar approach is adopted for sending models to clients, to reduce the overhead associated with model compression and transmission. When a model request is received, it is placed into the model handler's queue, while the socket is temporarily disabled. The model handler has a cache that contains models previously saved in the file system. If the requested model is already in the

cache, it is immediately sent to the client. If the model is not available, the request is added to the compression queue. Once compression is complete, the model transmission request is re-added to the model handler's queue for actual sending.

The cache plays a crucial role in the system's performance. For example, when the global model is updated, it is very likely to receive requests for the same model from multiple clients, and cache usage significantly reduces response times and computational overhead. In the future, this subsystem could be externalized from the central Server and implemented through a Content Delivery Network (CDN), further improving system distribution and scalability.

Synchronization Events

The management of sending events such as ForceSync and NewGlobalModel is handled through a publish-subscribe pattern. There is a special upgrade message that removes the connection from the normal epoll management and adds the socket to a listeners list. In this way, ownership of the connection is transferred to the aggregation thread.

Configuration and Customization

The configuration and customization of the framework to adapt it to any Federated Learning scenario or algorithm occurs through the definition of two functions by the user.

```
1 typedef struct
2 {
3     uint8_t type; // 0: NO, 1: YES, 2: WAIT
4     time_t until;
5 } agg_config_t;
6
7 agg_config_t should_aggregate_models(updates_t updates, time_t *last_aggregation, func_t
8     force_sync)
9
10 double get_update_weight(model_info_t local_model, model_t gobal_model)
```

The `should_aggregate_models` function defines the buffering strategy. The user, based on the updates ready to be aggregated, decides whether to aggregate the models immediately, not to aggregate and wait for subsequent updates, or to wait for a specified time period and perform aggregation if no updates are received within that time. A `force_sync` function is passed to allow the user to send a notification to clients that have not yet completed model training. The `get_update_weight` function, on the other hand, defines the aggregation strategy; it receives as input the local model's information and the global model and returns the weight that the local model should have in the

next averaging step. The model itself, in addition to the weights, also contains metadata that can be used to further customize the aggregation process. To implement a FedAvg algorithm, for example, metadata containing the size of the dataset on which the local model was trained is necessary. To ensure the correctness of the metadata, it is necessary to define a function (`is_valid_metadata`) that can be used to validate the content. Since this is a thesis aimed at studying the feasibility of the proposed solution, for now these functions must be defined within the source code, which requires knowledge of the C language and manual recompilation of the project. For the future, however, the idea is to distribute the pre-compiled application and allow customization through higher-level scripting languages, relying on libraries like Extism [Ext24], which allow the user to define these functions in any preferred language (Python, JS, C, C++, Java, Ruby, Go ... etc.). In addition to scripting capabilities, the idea is that the framework natively supports the most common strategies.

4.3 Communication Protocol

The client-server communication protocol necessary for implementing the solution proposed in this thesis is very simple and requires a limited number of messages. For this reason, we have opted for a simple implementation that does not use technologies like gRPC, HTTP, WebSocket, MPI, etc. For communication between client and server, we have therefore used TCP sockets with messages in a non-standard format optimized for this use case. Figure 4.5 shows the structure of a generic message.

Figure 4.5: Structure of a communication protocol message

The protocol consists of 4 main messages: Authentication, Global Model Request, Update Sending, Notification Channel Subscription.

Model Format The proposed framework is designed to be completely transparent to the user, allowing them to freely use any machine learning backend they desire, such as PyTorch, TensorFlow, or others. However, each of the main machine learning frameworks uses a proprietary format to save the state of trained models, and these formats are not optimized for federated learning contexts, where model weights are frequently transmitted between devices and efficient network bandwidth usage is crucial. In a federated learning context, model weights must be shared frequently between participating nodes and the central server. The continuous transmission of trained models represents a significant load on network bandwidth, making a strategy necessary that minimizes the volume of data transmitted. Furthermore, to support advanced federated optimization algorithms, such as Federated Averaging (FedAvg), it is essential to enrich the model with metadata that describe the training context, such as the size of the dataset used on each node. This information enables appropriate weighting of updates sent by each participant, thereby improving the precision and effectiveness of the optimization.

To meet these requirements, we have chosen to develop a custom file format, optimized both for efficiency in network bandwidth usage and for the integration of metadata and structural information

necessary for effective model update management in the federated learning context. Figure 4.6 illustrates the file structure.

Figure 4.6: Structure of the file representing the state of an ML network

The file format is designed with a two-component structure: a header and a body. This organization allows quick access to key model information from the first byte transmitted, enabling efficient processing even during transfer (this allows handling updates as a data stream). The header contains all the information necessary to describe the model and is structured to be uncompressed. This choice allows the server to access all essential information as soon as the first chunk of data is received, enabling optimized network management and immediate file interpretation.

The header consists of:

- File information: format version, sizes of various file segments, and flags describing properties such as compression, quantization, and the presence of optional sections.
- Metadata: a section dedicated to various types of information, such as strings, integers, or floats, that describe the model’s training context. This metadata can include details like the number of samples used in local training or the specific configuration of the node. This data enables proper calibration of model updates, particularly useful for aggregation algorithms like FedAvg, which require information on dataset size.
- Tensor structure description: an optional section that provides details on tensor structure, such

as dimensions and layout. This section can be disabled via a flag if the recipient already knows this information, further reducing the amount of transmitted data. Structural descriptions are useful to ensure that aggregation or model fusion operations are performed accurately, without risks of data misinterpretation.

The file body contains the tensor values, i.e., the model weights and parameters, in a sequential format organized in row-major order. This arrangement allows treating the weights as a single large vector, facilitating aggregation operations such as averaging between models: parameters can be summed directly without needing to know specific details about the internal tensor structure. This simplification makes the format highly flexible and suitable for federated environments, where model structures between nodes must be aligned quickly. Additionally, this structure allows sending the model in streaming mode without requiring the entire model to be held in memory; this is particularly helpful on the server side because it enables increasing the number of concurrent clients that can be managed.

The format is designed to facilitate both compression and quantization of data, two essential techniques for minimizing network bandwidth consumption. The header includes a field called `difff_model_version`, which indicates the global model version from which the current version derives. Thanks to this feature, model weights can be saved as a difference (or "diff") relative to a reference version, rather than as absolute values. This approach drastically reduces the amount of data, as many differences are close to zero, making the file easily compressible with lossless compression algorithms.

This incremental compression structure, combined with the ability to quantize weights (for example, using lower precision like `int8` instead of `float32`), allows further optimization of model transmission in the federated learning context, reducing network requirements without sacrificing the overall accuracy of the model.

Figure 4.7: File System-Based Client Approach

4.4 Client Software Architecture

The client software architecture is extremely simple, consisting of a library that hides interaction with the central server. Its interface is as minimal as possible, as seen in the code below; it is sufficient to import the library and define a Client.

```

1 token = "auth_token..."
2 store = BlobStore()
3 client = FLClient("coordinator.domain", store, token, backend="pytorch")
4 net = client.get_model()
5
6 client.train(rounds=N, dataloader)
  
```

Afterward, two functions are available: `get_model` allows downloading the global model and initializing the network in the selected backend; `train` automatically performs N rounds of federated learning. The model structure and the implementation of the training strategy are defined globally and provided by the central server. These functions are customizable during server configuration, but the idea is to automatically provide functions for the most common optimizations such as FedAvg, FedProx, FedNova, etc. It is still possible to completely rewrite the training function and use the event reception and model sending functions explicitly.

The idea for the future is to make the framework even more transparent and agnostic. One way to do this could be to create a solution that does not depend on the application's implementation technology. To achieve this, a daemon could be created that reads data from a file system folder and in the background performs federated learning. Additionally, the same daemon would be responsible for keeping the global model used updated. Figure 4.7 represents the high-level architecture of the proposal. With this solution, developing applications that use federated learning would be very simple, as the application would only need to save the collected data to a folder.

Chapter 5

Experimental Evaluation

Before proceeding with the implementation of the framework described in this thesis, we conducted a series of preliminary experiments to evaluate the empirical feasibility of our approach. As discussed in depth in Chapter 4, the framework requires the adoption of an asynchronous approach to meet the requirements of a system characterized by strong heterogeneity and not fully reliable communications. However, as discussed in section 2.6, the adoption of an asynchronous approach introduces numerous challenges related to model convergence and stability, issues that can be further exacerbated in the presence of heterogeneous Client configurations.

To evaluate the impact of asynchrony on the system, we conducted initial experiments in synchronous or hybrid contexts, progressively introducing more relaxed assumptions. This gradual approach allowed us to understand more deeply the critical issues arising from heterogeneity, providing a solid foundation for addressing the problems that emerge in asynchronous execution environments.

5.1 Test Architecture

To evaluate the proposed approach, we designed a test architecture on a cluster of 16 homogeneous nodes to conduct experiments in a distributed context with numerous Clients. This choice differs significantly from other federated learning simulation frameworks, such as Flower, which typically run simulations on a single machine using separate processes or threads to represent Clients. Our solution is designed to realistically replicate the operational conditions of a distributed system, thus offering greater fidelity to realistic scenarios and improved horizontal scalability.

Cluster Architecture

The distributed architecture consists of:

- A dedicated node for the Server Ticker (whose features will be introduced in the next section) and the Aggregator, for coordinating Clients and managing asynchronous updates.
- Fifteen Client nodes, each representing an independent entity of the federated system, which executes the local training cycle and communicates with the Aggregator.

Each node has an 8-core CPU with hyperthreading and sufficient memory to execute the assigned workloads. Communication between nodes occurs via a high-speed local Ethernet network. The proposed distributed architecture offers native scalability, making the framework suitable for experiments of increasing size without requiring structural modifications. In particular:

It is possible to add new Client nodes to the cluster with minimal impact on the existing infrastructure. The use of physical nodes allows full exploitation of hardware resources, improving performance and reducing the risk of bottlenecks due to the concurrent execution of numerous Clients on a single server. Thanks to the choice of running tests on a distributed cluster, our framework represents a more realistic and scalable approach compared to centralized simulation-based solutions, demonstrating its ability to operate effectively in complex and large-scale environments.

Architecture Components

The system is divided into three main components: the Server Ticker, the Clients, and an Aggregator (the framework Server extensively described in Chapter 4) that manages federated learning in a fully asynchronous mode.

Main components:

- Server Ticker: responsible for synchronizing Client behavior without directly participating in the aggregation process. Its main functions are:

- Tick Sending: sends periodic signals (ticks) to all connected Clients, indicating the start of a new computation cycle.
- Client Synchronization: waits for acks from Clients, which confirm receipt of the tick. Before sending a new tick, the Server Ticker waits for Clients to complete the current cycle or handle any delays.

The Server Ticker does not interact with the global model nor collect updates: its function is exclusively to coordinate Clients by marking time.

- Client: Each cluster node runs one or more Client instances, which are responsible for: a) receiving the global model from the Aggregator; b) executing the local training cycle; c) sending model updates to the Aggregator.

The synchronous or asynchronous behavior depends directly on the Clients. The latter can:

1. send an immediate ack to the received tick, allowing the Server Ticker to proceed to the next cycle (asynchronous behavior).
2. delay the ack sending, introducing controlled stalls in the system or parts of it, thereby forcing synchronization of only certain phases of federated learning.

- Aggregator: a completely asynchronous component that exclusively manages receiving updates from Clients, aggregation, and distribution of global models. There is no direct coordination between Aggregator and Server Ticker since Client synchronization is managed exclusively by the Ticker.

The test architecture is shown at a high level in Figure 5.1

Figure 5.1: Test Architecture

5.2 Heterogeneity Issues in Synchronous Contexts

In most research papers, the topic of computational system heterogeneity for Federated Averaging (FedAvg) is addressed simply by ignoring delayed updates. Delayed updates are those that were started from a version of the global model that is no longer the latest at the time of their submission. Clients that send delayed updates are called stragglers. Since the ultimate goal is to develop an asynchronous system, we wanted to understand the impact on convergence when such updates are still considered.

To do this, in this section we study the impact of the presence of delays and the aggregation of outdated updates by incrementally adding heterogeneity issues (both statistical and systemic). To confirm the results of the experiments, each one was repeated 8 times; for practicality and compactness, below only the graphs from one of them will be reported.

Delay Patterns

To make the experiments discussed below deterministic and therefore replicable, we defined 3 main delay patterns:

- **Sampling:** We consider N_t as the number of active Clients in round t , $\lceil N_t * p \rceil$ is the number of straggler Clients in that round t .
- **Latency:** This pattern uses two parameters L, p : L describes the amount of delay that a straggler client has relative to the global model. For example, $L = 2$ means that a straggler Client sends an update related to a global model that is now two generations old. p describes the probability that a Client is a straggler. For example, if there are 100 Clients and $p = 0.5$, 50 Clients are stragglers. This pattern helps us understand how the stability of model convergence varies when there are different types of Clients that have different processing times throughout the entire federated learning.
- **Random:** This pattern uses a pseudo-random number generator. In each round, each client has a probability p of being delayed. The number of delay generations is thus given by the geometric distribution with parameter $1 - p$.

Stragglers with IID Data

To lay the groundwork and a baseline reference for the following sections, we started with the base case: synchronous learning on IID data. The approach used is not theoretically completely synchronous but is in practice: even though updates related to old versions of the global model are allowed. In fact, a new global model is not produced every time an update is received, but rather when all updates from non-straggler Clients are received.

For the first tests, we used the MNIST dataset (image recognition ML) and AGNews (text classification ML). We used AGNews to verify the independence of the results from the type of ML and dataset. For compactness, from now on only the MNIST case will be shown (AGNews confirms the same trend). The datasets were evenly divided among N Clients. By evenly, we mean that each client has the same number of samples for each class. To notice only the effect of stragglers and isolate the variable of system heterogeneity, we used the same learning parameters for each client (Epochs=6, BatchSize=256, LearningRate=0.01).

Since the purpose of the thesis is to propose a framework capable of handling a large number of clients, we used 100 Clients, unlike studies conducted in other research such as [SLS⁺18] where a limited number of Clients is used (in the range of a few dozen: $Client \in [10, 30]$).

L/p	0	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.6
0	L 0, p 0	L 0, p 0.1	L 0, p 0.2	L 0, p 0.4	L 0, p 0.6
2	L 2, p 0	L 2, p 0.1	L 2, p 0.2	L 2, p 0.4	L 2, p 0.6
4	L 4, p 0	L 4, p 0.1	L 4, p 0.2	L 4, p 0.4	L 4, p 0.6
8	L 8, p 0	L 8, p 0.1	L 8, p 0.2	L 8, p 0.4	L 8, p 0.6

Table 5.1: Latency-type delay parameters tested on IID data

We repeated the experiment by varying the delay patterns. Table 5.1 shows the parameters of the tests performed with the Latency delay pattern (described in the previous section). In addition to the Latency pattern, we ran the tests with the Random pattern following the same probabilities p .

Since the results are very homogeneous among themselves, Figure 5.2 presents the most relevant results. From the results, it can be deduced that allowing the aggregation of outdated updates with i.i.d data does not affect the final model accuracy. Already from round 50 the delta is so close to 0 that it becomes negligible. By delta, we mean the difference between the accuracy of the model trained in a context without delays and the accuracy of the model trained with a specific delay pattern.

Stragglers with Non-Uniformly Distributed Data

What happens, however, if the distribution of data types is not uniform? We repeated the experiment with a non-uniform distribution of labels in each local dataset (the label distribution is shown in Figure 5.3). The sample distribution, as can be seen, is very skewed toward a single class; we wanted to experiment with the extreme case to see how much this variable can potentially impact model convergence as the number of stragglers varies. As shown in Figure 5.4, the final convergence is not affected by the non-uniform distribution of sample types in the local datasets. Furthermore, in Figure 5.5, it can be seen that the presence of stragglers does not cause major problems, or rather, does not cause any at all; in fact, the experiments performed with various delay patterns show, with a reasonable amount of variance, the same trend as the case with no delays.

Stragglers in Non-IID Case

So far, we have only tested one case of statistical heterogeneity: data distribution. What happens if the local models are not the same, i.e., if there is no unique global objective function?

To test how convergence changes when local models are heterogeneous among themselves, we replicated the experiments proposed in [SLS⁺18]. These experiments involve using Federated Learning to train logistic regression on synthetic datasets.

Figure 5.2: Model accuracy delta over the course of training rounds compared to training without stragglers with i.i.d data.

$$\text{delta}(\text{round}) = \text{accuracy}_{\text{no_strag}}(\text{round}) - \text{accuracy}_{\text{strag}}(\text{round})$$

The datasets are generated from two parameters α and β where the first controls how different the local models are from each other and the second how non-uniformly the data are distributed (the IID case is added as a benchmark reference).

To generate these datasets, we used the software artifact provided by the authors ¹, using the same seeds for the pseudo-random number generators to obtain exactly the same datasets used.

First, as a benchmark, we run the test by removing delays and thus the presence of straggler Clients. From Figure 5.6, it is evident how the stability of the global model is compromised in non-IID cases and how it is proportionally unstable as statistical heterogeneity increases. However, using more reasonable parameters such as a larger batch size or a lower learning rate can restore model stability. Another option is to use optimizations of the classic FedAvg algorithm like FedProx, which solves instability problems as shown in the cited article. These solutions are efficient and allow ensuring in practice the convergence of the global model even in heterogeneous situations.

¹<https://github.com/litian96/FedProx>

Figure 5.3: Non-uniform label distributions. The x -axis indicates the class (label) and the y -axis the portion of the local dataset formed by samples of that class.

For clarity, on the left is shown the case of a single Client, which has a "bias" toward class 5. On the right are shown all the Clients. Although the Clients used in our tests are 100, there are only 10 types of sample distributions, since the MNIST dataset consists of 10 classes. Each type of dataset will therefore be used by $\lceil N_{client}/N_{class} \rceil$

Figure 5.4: Accuracy of models trained without delays. As can be seen, the label distribution does not affect either the final model performance or the convergence speed.

What happens if we reintroduce the presence of stragglers? We repeated the experiments in two configurations:

- Outdated update discard: Whenever a Client is late with its update, the result of its training is discarded. Regarding the delay pattern, these experiments use Sampling. The results are shown in Figure 5.7
- Aggregation of outdated updates: When a delayed Client update arrives, the outdated result is

Figure 5.5: Model accuracy delta over the course of training rounds compared to training without stragglers with non-uniformly distributed data.

$$\text{delta}(\text{round}) = \text{accuracy}_{\text{no_strag}}(\text{round}) - \text{accuracy}_{\text{strag}}(\text{round})$$

aggregated together with the results in line with the global model. Regarding the delay pattern, these experiments use the Random scheme. In Figure 5.8 are shown the FedAvg results while in Figure 5.9 those of FedProx.

In the case of discarding outdated updates, a greater instability of global model convergence is noted compared to the absence of stragglers (Figure 5.6), but using more moderate training parameters such as a lower learning rate solves the problem. In the case of aggregating outdated updates, however, there is greater instability compared to the discard technique; in this case, adapting the training parameters is not sufficient, while using techniques like FedProx solves the instability problem. In fact, as shown in Figure 5.9, it is evident how effective FedProx is in these cases, remaining stable even with non-optimal parameterizations. It should also be noted how the IID case significantly slows down convergence in the case of strong straggler presence and when using very limited learning rates.

Figure 5.6: FedAvg results with non-IID data, on the left with batch size 10 while on the right with batch size 50; in the figure below are reported the results in the case of learning rate 0.001 with batch size 50

Stragglers with Heterogeneous Training Parameters

So far, we have assumed that each Client performs the same amount of global work, and we have noted that in this configuration, although the presence of stragglers affects model stability, it is easily manageable with small adjustments in the learning parameter configuration.

What happens if we relax this assumption and allow Clients to perform a variable amount of work?

To enable this experiment, we removed the stragglers and allowed each Client to perform a variable amount of work in terms of epochs. In this way, we removed the straggler phenomenon by allowing these Clients to perform less work to avoid being late. As shown in the paper [SLS⁺18],

Figure 5.7: FedAvg results with presence of 50% stragglers in each round with non-IID data and drop of delayed Clients. On the left are reported the results in case of learning rate 0.01 while on the right the cases with learning rate 0.001

Figure 5.8: FedAvg results with presence of 40% stragglers with the Random delay pattern with non-IID data. On the left are reported the results in case of learning rate 0.01 while on the right the cases with learning rate 0.001

and as replicated in our tests in Figure 5.10, FedAvg in non-IID conditions tends to lose convergence stability and exhibits the objective inconsistency problem explained in detail in the Computational System Heterogeneity section 2.3. FedProx in this case, however, by adding a proximity parameter and thus limiting the effects of updates following different directions, effectively masks the system heterogeneity problem. FedProx is not the only possible optimization; in fact, there are solutions like FedNova [WLL⁺20], FedAvgM [HQB19], and HySync [SLW⁺20] that use different approaches

Figure 5.9: FedProx results with presence of 40% stragglers using Random delay pattern with non-IID data. On the left are reported the results in case of learning rate 0.01 and batch size 10 while on the right the cases with learning rate 0.001 and batch size 50

but aimed at improving model convergence stability and specifically at mitigating the objective inconsistency problem.

Figure 5.10: Training loss of FedAvg and FedProx when Clients perform a variable number of epochs.

5.3 Heterogeneity Issues in Asynchronous Contexts

Having explored the effects of heterogeneity in synchronous contexts, we have acquired the knowledge and benchmarks necessary to systematically evaluate the asynchronous approach. The next step involves defining a method that allows simulating the asynchronous execution of Clients in a controlled and repeatable environment. This approach is essential for analyzing asynchronous dynamics, identifying any critical issues, and optimizing aggregation and Client management strategies, taking into account their heterogeneous characteristics.

Modeling Asynchronous Updates and Client Selection

To obtain realistic update sending behavior, we used a pseudo-random number generator with a constant seed. Since the learning is completely asynchronous, the concept of rounds disappears. We define the iteration of our simulation as a *tick*. Each tick represents an abstract variable time span, as it simulates the passage of time between client model submissions, which is arbitrarily non-uniform. For the purpose of the tests, the time intervals between one update and another are not of interest. Since the concept of rounds no longer exists, on the x -axis we indicate the versions of the global model (numbered from 0 to n : from the oldest to the newest).

At each tick, a Client is randomly selected to send an update. The selected Client performs e epochs of training, which, for the purpose of this experiment, is a random number between $([5, 20])^2$. Additionally, the selected client trains the model based on l previous versions of the global model (where l can be 0, i.e., the latest model), to simulate the effect of outdated updates. The parameter l is related to a geometric distribution with parameter p (distribution described by the formula $P(l = n) = p^n$). For executing this experiment, we fixed $p = 0.8$ as a very high delay probability that allows us to study the most extreme case.

For computational complexity reasons and the need for comparison with the previous phase, we used synthetic datasets generated as described in the preceding section. The use of these synthetic datasets also allows us to have control over statistical heterogeneity variables.

Instability Issues and Solutions

As a first experiment, we evaluated the case of purely asynchronous aggregation: Every time an update is received by the aggregator, it immediately generates the new global model. In Figure 5.11 are shown the results. As noted, in the case of IID data, no problems are encountered, but as soon as a margin of heterogeneity is introduced, the model convergence becomes completely unstable.

Figure 5.11: Accuracy of completely asynchronous training.

To compensate for this instability, we introduced the FedBuff technique [NMZ⁺21], which consists

²Epochs lower than 5 may prove insufficient to allow the model to learn significantly from the client’s local data, leading to an update that is little useful or even detrimental to the global model. On the other hand, performing more than 20 epochs may not be necessary, as federated learning is based on frequent updates from clients, and a high number of epochs per update could lead to excessive computational overload without providing substantial improvements to the global model.

of "buffering" the updates. As soon as an update arrives, it is placed in the buffer; if there are at least N pending updates, the new model is generated; otherwise, it waits for new updates. The proposed framework natively supports this operation; in fact, for performance reasons, updates are automatically placed in a queue. We therefore repeated the experiment applying FedBuff with $N = 10$. As seen in Figure 5.12, where the results are shown, this optimization is decidedly efficient and allows solving instability problems. In the case of greater heterogeneity ($\alpha = 1, \beta = 1$), negative peaks in the model accuracy are noted; these are probably related to the objective inconsistency problem: a new version involves models that all present a strong "bias," which causes the global model to shift toward the "bias" and thus move away from the global objective function.

Figure 5.12: Accuracy of asynchronous training with FedBuff $N = 10$

Combination of FedBuff and FedProx

Although FedBuff may already be potentially sufficient to solve instability problems, it is possible to combine this technique with other techniques like FedProx. Therefore, we repeated the experiment keeping $N = 10$ and integrating FedProx with parameter $\mu = 1$. As seen from Figure 5.13, the small instabilities that had been obtained with the simple application of FedBuff have disappeared. As a side effect, however, there is a considerable slowdown in convergence in the case of IID data, this result is in line with expectations; in fact, this phenomenon is also highlighted in the article in which FedProx is proposed [SLS⁺18]

Figure 5.13: Accuracy of asynchronous training with FedBuff $N = 10$ and FedProx $\mu = 1$

5.4 Framework Benchmarks

To evaluate the performance of the framework implemented in this thesis, we conducted benchmarks. As a reference metric, we used the number of operations per second (OPS) that the system can handle to assess the server’s throughput capabilities. We created two types of operations that the test Clients can perform: 1) the first involves connecting to the server, authenticating, and downloading the latest version of the model; 2) the second involves connecting, authenticating, and sending a local update. Each Client will alternate between performing the two operations. To make the test representative of a real Federated Learning context, we considered it reasonable to assume that each federated device takes on the order of minutes to train the local model. Therefore, it is very unlikely that computing a new model every second or fraction of a second would be useful for federated learning purposes. Consequently, we configured the central server to aggregate results every 10 seconds.

The tests were conducted with varying degrees of parallelism to evaluate the framework’s scalability: 1, 2, 4, 8 threads, considering that the aggregator always resides on a separate thread. Each test was repeated 10 times, and the final results are the average of the repeated trials.

Figure 5.14 presents the obtained results. As can be seen, already with 4 threads, the system is capable of handling approximately 100,000 OPS. Assuming that a Client is capable of generating an update every hour, the system can handle an order-of-magnitude number of devices on the order of a million. The framework’s performance stops scaling already with 4 threads. This behavior is due to the saturation of the cluster’s network resources on which the tests were conducted. From a theoretical standpoint, the server is designed to scale linearly with the number of threads,

Figure 5.14: Framework benchmarks in terms of operations per second manageable as the degree of parallelism varies. The indicated line shows the resource utilization efficiency expressed as a percentage, indicating how well the system is able to utilize available resources as the number of threads used changes.

thanks to the parallelized design and the separate thread dedicated to aggregation. However, the limitations of the available hardware resources, particularly those related to network bandwidth and latency, represented a bottleneck for overall performance. Therefore, the presented results should be considered partial and representative only of the framework’s capabilities within the specific test context. As future development, we plan to evaluate the framework’s performance on higher-bandwidth interconnection networks.

5.5 Considerations

Although statistical and systemic heterogeneity pose issues at the level of model convergence, in the first section of experimentation we have empirically shown how these, in synchronous contexts, are easily manageable using appropriate training parameter configurations and optimization techniques where necessary.

In asynchronous contexts, however, compared to synchronous ones, statistical and systemic heterogeneity create greater instability problems. Using a completely asynchronous approach (where a new version of the global model is generated for every received update), we noted that the model diverges in practice in cases where the IID data assumption is not met. However, we observed significant improvements in using hybrid approaches like FedBuff [NMZ⁺21], which allow for considerable stabilization of model convergence.

Despite the notable improvements obtained with FedBuff [NMZ⁺21], in cases of high heterogeneity, model stability issues remain, albeit attenuated, related to the objective inconsistency phenomenon [WLL⁺20] (an issue discussed in detail in the Background chapter 2).

To solve the model instability problem in highly heterogeneous contexts, we combined FedBuff [NMZ⁺21] with FedProx [SLS⁺18]. This combination completely eliminated the objective inconsistency problem.

The work carried out demonstrates that, although managing heterogeneity in synchronous and asynchronous contexts may seem like a complex challenge, the adoption of appropriate strategies allows these problems to be effectively addressed and resolved, ensuring the stability and convergence of the global model.

In addition to the results related to global model convergence, these experiments have demonstrated that the developed framework³ has proven capable of reproducing results presented in scientific articles using simulators, such as [SLS⁺18] and [NMZ⁺21], in real and physically distributed environments. The framework has revealed itself to be sufficiently flexible to introduce multiple techniques and verify their effectiveness (even in synchronous contexts that remain outside the main scope of the software itself). Its modular architecture has facilitated the integration of various strategies, particularly that of FedBuff, making its implementation simple and effective. In fact, update buffering is already a native feature of the framework, designed to optimize performance. The frame-

³<https://github.com/mamodev/Async-Federated-Learning>

work, in addition to considerable flexibility, has demonstrated the ability to handle large workloads: on the order of hundreds of thousands of OPS.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Future Developments

In recent years, Federated Learning (FL) has shown great potential to overcome the limitations of traditional Machine Learning, offering innovative solutions in terms of data privacy and scalability. However, its practical application, especially in contexts with heterogeneous devices, presents significant challenges related to different device capabilities, communication complexity, and distributed management. In this thesis, we addressed these issues by proposing a framework¹ designed to simplify the adoption of asynchronous Federated Learning, allowing developers to focus on key aspects such as model definition and data analysis, without having to deal with underlying technical complexities.

Throughout this work, we first introduced Federated Learning, its challenges (such as data and computational system heterogeneity) and some of the possible architectures. After providing a complete overview of the necessary background, we analyzed the solutions currently available on the market, evaluating their strengths and weaknesses, and highlighted a lack of appropriate options for cross-device and highly heterogeneous contexts on a large scale (hundreds of thousands of Clients). After clarifying the motivations that guided the development of the framework¹ that is the subject of this thesis, we described its design and software architecture in detail. Finally, we conducted extensive experimentation to validate the software's operation itself, successfully replicating experiments present in academic papers such as [SLS⁺18]. We also empirically demonstrated that, although managing heterogeneity in synchronous and asynchronous contexts may seem a complex challenge, the adoption of appropriate strategies allows effectively addressing and resolving these problems, ensuring the stability and convergence of the global model. The developed framework¹ stands out for its focus on efficiency and flexibility. The choice to optimize performance, reducing computational

¹Source code: <https://github.com/mamodev/Async-Federated-Learnig>

load and improving resource management, enables superior scalability compared to many existing solutions we analyzed. Communication between devices has also been optimized to ensure greater system smoothness and responsiveness, allowing effective management of numerous simultaneously connected devices. Furthermore, the framework¹ offers customization possibilities, allowing adaptation of aggregation strategies to specific developer needs. Experimental tests have demonstrated how this framework¹ makes the development of asynchronous Federated Learning applications trivial, successfully addressing heterogeneity and scalability issues typical of distributed devices.

Future Developments

The developed framework¹ offers numerous possibilities for evolution to address Federated Learning challenges even more effectively. A promising direction is the transition to a more decentralized and resilient architecture, with the integration of mechanisms to improve system reliability and scalability. The adoption of advanced techniques to optimize communications and reduce bandwidth consumption represents another potential area for improvement.

A further area of development concerns the integration of advanced tools for privacy protection, such as advanced encryption or differential privacy, which offer even stronger guarantees on the secure handling of data. Additionally, extending support to a wider range of learning models, including unsupervised models and reinforcement learning, could make the framework¹ even more versatile and applicable in different contexts.

Finally, improving accessibility through comprehensive documentation and intuitive interfaces could broaden the audience of potential users. The effectiveness of the framework¹ could be further validated through large-scale tests in collaboration with industrial or academic entities, to demonstrate its ability to operate with a high number of devices in real environments.

Final Considerations

I believe that the proposed framework, available on GitHub¹, represents a step forward toward a Federated Learning that is more accessible even to developers not expert in infrastructures and distributed systems. In its design and development phase, we effectively addressed the challenges related to heterogeneity and scalability, providing developers with a flexible and intuitive solution for implementing applications that respect privacy and make the best use of heterogeneous device resources. With the potential future developments described in the previous section, the goal is to further expand the technological and usage capabilities of the developed framework, making it an important element for innovation in the field of Federated Learning, promoting collaboration, security, and efficiency in increasingly complex distributed environments.

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